

Condition of Sparingly Soluble Substances when formed in Presence of a Gel : Silver Bromide, Silver Iodide, and Silver Cyanide in Gelatine.

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In view of the fact that many of the experiments on Liesegang-ring formation in the laboratory are carried out in presence of gels, it is of considerable importance to know exactly the condition in which sparingly soluble substances exist in these gels when freshly formed.

We are of opinion that sparingly soluble substances when formed in gels do exist mainly in the colloidal state; while many believe that they exist in the supersaturated condition. Thus Freundlich states, "The Ag_2CrO_4 (and $\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$) formed by the diffusion of silver nitrate into the gelatine containing the bichromate remains in supersaturated solution." The above view of Freundlich is directly based on Ostwald's assumption that supersaturation plays an important part in the formation of Liesegang rings in gels.

We have shown experimentally from electric conductivity measurements that the above view of Freundlich is incorrect and that both silver chromate and chloride in gelatine exist mainly in the colloidal condition.

Recently Bolam and Mackenzie (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 67, 160) have confirmed the conclusions arrived at previously by Williams and Mackenzie that silver chromate in gelatine exists in the ionic state. But we have already pointed out (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 175) from a study of the experimental results of Bolam and Mackenzie that in majority of cases the amount of silver present in the ionic state is approximately only 40% of the total quantity. We are of opinion that the remaining two-thirds of silver which does not exist in the ionic state, remains in a colloidal condition. Hence the measurements of Bolam and Mackenzie are in support of our views.

Moreover, in view of the high protective action of gelatine it is only natural that the sparingly soluble substances when formed in

presence of the above gel should remain in the colloidal condition and not give rise to supersaturated solution. Thus, to quote Freundlich, "in sufficiently concentrated solutions of gelatine, it is possible to prevent the separation of practically every precipitate which is difficultly soluble in water and to retain it colloiddally dispersed in solution." Svedberg was actually able to prepare colloidal solutions of silver chloride and bromide and Prussian blue by precipitating them in gelatine. Consequently, it is difficult to understand how substances like silver chloride, silver chromate, etc., can remain in the supersaturated condition in gelatine.

An objection may be raised that due to the presence of a viscous medium, the electric conductivities will be greatly reduced and, therefore, the conclusions drawn from them may not be accurate. But Arrhenius proved long ago that the electric conductivities of substances like hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, etc., when set in gelatine are practically the same as in aqueous solutions. Moreover, electric conductivities in all cases are measured in presence of the same viscous medium. Therefore, any change which the conductivities suffer due to the presence of the viscous medium affects all the cases equally, and does not change the final conclusions.

In this paper we have carefully determined the electric conductivities of silver chloride, bromide and cyanide in gelatine. We have also determined the concentrations of the silver ions in the case of the above three salts in gelatine by *E. M. F.* measurements. The experimental results obtained are in complete agreement with the conclusions arrived at in previous papers.

The reason why the above salts of silver are chosen is that these salts are not affected like silver chromate by the hydrogen-ion concentration of the medium, and therefore, the percentage of silver in the ionic condition should be far less than that found by Bolam and Mackenzie with silver chromate. This conclusion of ours has been proved to be correct from the results recorded in this paper.

Experiments were undertaken to find out the electric conductivities of different amounts of silver bromide, silver iodide and silver cyanide in gelatine at 20°. Nelson's "A₂-gelatine" was used and it was purified by the method of J. Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1918, 1, 285) to give an ash-free gelatine, which has been employed in all the experiments described in this paper.

As the sparingly soluble silver salts were obtained by the addition of equivalent quantities of silver nitrate and potassium salt of the corresponding acid, in every case, an equivalent amount of potassium nitrate was also produced. In order to ascertain the conductivity of the sparingly silver salt alone, the conductivity of an equivalent concentration of potassium nitrate in gelatine was determined under identical conditions.

A typical result of the conductivity measurements obtained with silver bromide is shown in Table I. Exactly similar results were obtained with other concentrations of the sparingly soluble salt. The results obtained are summarised in Table II. From the conductivity measurements given in Table I, the conductivity of silver bromide as determined by experiment can be ascertained by simply subtracting the conductivity of potassium nitrate from that of the mixture of potassium bromide and silver nitrate. If it is assumed that the whole of AgBr. remains in the ionic condition and not in the colloidal state, then its conductivity should be equal to the sum of the conductivities of potassium bromide and silver nitrate *less* the conductivity of potassium nitrate alone. Table II contains results calculated on the basis of the above considerations.

Electric conductivity of AgBr in gelatine.

TABLE I.

Temperature at which the experiments were performed.	20°.
Concentrations of AgBr, AgNO ₃ , KBr, KNO ₃	N/800.
Concentration of gelatine solution.	0.5 gm. per 100 c.c.
Conductivity of water.	2.085×10^{-6} mhos.
Conductivity of gelatine.	0.518×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + AgNO ₃	1.703×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + KBr.	2.000×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine AgNO ₃ + KBr.	1.972×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + KNO ₃	1.992×10^{-4} "

TABLE II.

Concentration of AgBr.	Observed conductivity.	Conductivity calc. from exp. results assuming AgBr to be wholly in the ionic state.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
N/800	-0.020×10^{-4} mhos.	1.711×10^{-4}	nil
N/400	-0.013×10^{-4} "	2.790×10^{-4}	nil
N/200	0.009×10^{-4} "	10.843×10^{-4}	0.8

In the above experiments the conductivity of gelatine is far less than those which were used in experiments recorded in previous papers.

From results recorded in Table II, it is evident that if the whole of the silver bromide were present in the ionic condition, the conductivity observed would have been much greater than the values actually obtained. As a matter of fact, in the majority of cases investigated, the *minus* sign in the column of observed conductivity, indicates that the conductivity of a mixture of silver bromide and potassium nitrate is less than that of the latter alone.

Hence the foregoing experimental results lead us to the conclusion that silver bromide formed in gelatine by the interaction of equivalent quantities of silver nitrate and potassium bromide exists mainly in the colloidal state.

Exactly similar experiments were conducted with silver iodide in gelatine. The results obtained are given in Tables III and IV.

Electric conductivity of silver iodide in gelatine.

TABLE III.

Temperature at which the experiments were performed.	26°.
Concentrations of AgI, AgNO ₃ , KI, KNO ₃	N/800.
Concentration of gelatine solution.	0.5 gm. per 100 c.c.
Conductivity of water.	2.160×10^{-6} mhos.
Conductivity of gelatine.	0.408×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + AgNO ₃	1.578×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + KI.	1.708×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + AgNO ₃ + KI.	1.956×10^{-4} "
Conductivity of gelatine + KNO ₃	1.998×10^{-4} "

TABLE IV.

Concentration of AgBr.	Observed conductivity.	Conductivity calc. from exp. results assuming AgBr to be wholly in the ionic state.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
N/800	-0.087×10^{-4} mhos.	0.995×10^{-6} mhos.	Nd.
N/400	-0.108×10^{-4} "	2.197×10^{-4} "	"
N/200	-0.124×10^{-4} "	5.118×10^{-4} "	"
N/100	-0.200×10^{-4} "	10.662×10^{-4} "	"

From the above table it is clear that silver iodide has always a negative value for its observed conductivity. In other words, the conductivity of a mixture of silver iodide and potassium nitrate is always *less* than that of the latter alone in gelatine. This lowering in the conductivity is certainly due to the fact that somehow a portion of potassium nitrate has been removed from the field of action, thereby lowering its effective concentration. This is most probably due to the adsorption of potassium nitrate by silver iodide precipitate during formation.

Exactly similar results have also been obtained with silver cyanide in gelatine. The values obtained are summarised in Tables V and VI.

TABLE V.

Temperature at which the experiments were performed	..	20°.
Concentration of AgCN, AgNO ₃ , KCN, KNO ₃	...	N/800.
Concentration of gelatine solution	...	0.5 gm. in 100 c.c.
Conductivity of water	...	2.620 × 10 ⁻⁶ mhos.
Conductivity of gelatine	...	0.511 × 10 ⁻⁴ "
Conductivity of gelatine + AgNO ₃	...	1.707 × 10 ⁻⁴ "
Conductivity of gelatine + KCN	...	1.250 × 10 ⁻⁴ "
Conductivity of gelatine + AgNO ₃ + KCN	...	1.945 × 10 ⁻⁴ "
Conductivity of gelatine + KNO ₃	...	1.940 × 10 ⁻⁴ "

TABLE VI.

Concentration of AgCN.	Observed conductivity.	Conductivity calc. from exp. results assuming AgCN to be wholly in the ionic state.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
N/800	0.006 × 10 ⁻⁴ mhos.	0.9683 × 10 ⁻⁴ mhos.	0.62
N/400	0.058 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	3.4830 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	1.60
N/200	0.066 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	8.4396 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	1.92
N/100	0.21 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	8.4460 × 10 ⁻⁴ "	2.50

From the above table it will be seen that if silver cyanide were present wholly in the ionic condition, the observed conductivities should have been much greater than the values actually obtained. In no case the percentage of silver cyanide present in the ionic condition is greater than 2.5% as is clear from the values given in the last line of the above table. Hence more than 95% of silver cyanide is present in a state other than ionic. We are of opinion that this major portion of the sparingly soluble salt is in the colloidal state.

Conclusions drawn from the Conductivity Experiments.

From Tables II, IV and VI it will be evident that silver bromide, iodide and cyanide have much less electric conductivities than they should have if they were wholly in the ionic state.

The simultaneous production of an equivalent amount of potassium nitrate and the possibility of its adsorption by the freshly prepared sparingly soluble silver salts investigated during the course of their formation, may affect the observed conductivity of these salts. Hence in all cases the observed conductivity may be slightly less than that which should be found out if there were no adsorption of potassium nitrate and therefore, it might be argued that the evidence brought forward by electric conductivity determinations as to the condition in which the sparingly soluble salts are present when formed in gelatine may not exactly represent the true state, and the percentage of silver present in the ionic state may be increased. But the magnitude of the increase introduced will not be appreciably large in view of the fact that the adsorption of potassium nitrate by sparingly soluble silver salts has been found to be not very great. Mukherjee and Kundu (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 835) have determined the adsorption of electrolytes by pure silver iodide, and they are of opinion that of the cations—Ag, K, Ba, Ca and Al,—the order of adsorption is $Ag > Al > Ba : Ca > K$ or in other words, K is least adsorbed of all the cations investigated. Among the anions investigated the order of adsorption appears to be $Br > NO_3 > Cl > SO_4$.

Beekley and Taylor (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1942) have recently measured by analytical methods the adsorption of ions by precipitated AgI. They have found out the order of adsorption to be benzoate $>$ acetate $>$ nitrite $>$ nitrate $>$ chlorate $>$ perchlorate.

The authors employed soluble silver salts of the above acids for determining the adsorption, and their results with silver nitrate are given below.

Silver Iodide. Preparation No. 6. Temp. 25°.

<i>M</i>	<i>C₀</i>	<i>C₁</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>a</i>
78.289	0.008068	0.007944	2.874	0.0029
71.129	0.009787	0.00689	2.818	0.0030

where *M* = the weight of the solution ;

C₀ = the initial concentration in millimoles per gram of soln. ;

C₁ = the equilibrium " " " " " " "

m = the weight of silver iodide;

a = the amount of adsorption salt in millimoles per gram of silver iodide.

The amount of adsorption was calculated from the formula,

$$a = \frac{M(C_0 - C_1)}{m}$$

From the above table we have calculated the following results:—

Amount of AgNO_3 in one gram of the solution = 1.369×10^{-3} g.

Amount of AgI in 80 c.c. = 2.873 g.

Percentage of adsorption of AgNO_3 per gram of AgI = 0.49.

In our experiments the concentration of potassium nitrate was 8.08×10^{-3} g. in 80 c.c. of the solution while the amount of silver iodide was never more than 0.0469 g. With this quantity of silver iodide the adsorption of the nitrate should be considerably lower than that found by Beekley and Taylor. Moreover, according to Mukherjee and Kundu the adsorption of potassium nitrate is lower than that of silver nitrate. Hence it can be safely asserted that the quantity of potassium nitrate adsorbed will be considerably less than that of silver nitrate (0.49%) as calculated from Beekley and Taylor's data.

Therefore, the error introduced due to the adsorption of potassium nitrate (which is simultaneously produced) by the silver salts will not be great and the results obtained can be easily taken to give a fairly accurate idea of the state in which these sparingly soluble silver salts do exist when formed in presence of gelatine.

From the above results on the electric conductivity, it can be safely deduced that more than 95% of silver bromide, iodide and cyanide remain in a condition other than ionic in gelatine. We are of opinion that these large quantities of silver salts remain in a colloidal state.

In this connection, it is of interest to note the conclusions arrived at by Bolam in a recent paper (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 24, 461) that lead iodide in agar remains in a supersaturated condition. As the observed conductivity of lead iodide in agar increases with an increase in the concentration of the salt and can reach a value almost three times that of the initial concentration, it has been assumed that lead

iodide exists in the supersaturated state. This assumption is further strengthened by the observation that the conductivities at higher concentrations of lead iodide in agar are greater than that of a saturated solution of the salt prepared by dissolving a freshly prepared precipitate of lead iodide in conductivity water.

The above simply proves that in concentrated solutions of lead iodide in agar, a part of the salt is in the ionic condition. It does not prove that all or what part of the salt is in the ionic state.

We have emphasised in previous papers that the proper method to know exactly what portion of the sparingly soluble salt remains in the ionic state, is first to find out the conductivity of the salt assuming it to exist wholly as ions, and then to compare this value with the conductivity actually found out by direct experimental determinations. The former value can be calculated from the conductivities of each of the reacting electrolytes, and in this particular example, it is equal to the *sum* of the electric conductivities of lead nitrate and potassium iodide in agar *less* that of potassium nitrate also in agar. Bolam has simply determined the latter values and compared these values among themselves instead of with those calculated on the assumption that the salt exists wholly in the ionic condition.

The following table gives a comparison of the two sets of values as found by Bolam himself. The conductivities of lead iodide ($K_1 - K_2$) as determined by direct experiments have been taken from the last column of Tables III and IV of Bolam's paper, whilst the values for the conductivities of lead nitrate, potassium iodide and potassium nitrate have been calculated from the observations recorded in Table VI of the above paper.

TABLE VII.

Electric conductivities of PbI₂ of such concentrations as remain colourless in agar.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Milli-equi- valents.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	KI	KNO ₃ K ₂	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + KI K ₁	PbI ₂ observed K ₁ - K ₂	PbI ₂ calcula- ted wholly as ions (2 + 3) - 4.	Diffe- rence (7 - 6)	Percentage of PbI ₂ present in the ionic state. 99.3
3.173	288	431	412	617	305	307	2	86
7.911	769	1086	1020	1723	703	815	112	86
12.62	1233	1682	1612	2496	836	1303	418	67
				2429	817	1303	486	62
				2347	735	1303	568	56
				2306	684	1303	619	52

From the above table it is clear that the percentage of lead iodide in the ionic state decreases as the concentration of lead iodide increases—a conclusion which is exactly opposite to that of Bolam deduced from a consideration of the values given in column 7 only of the above table. Though the percentage of lead iodide in the ionic state appreciably decreases, it is certainly more than what we should ordinarily get. In our opinion, the large value of $K_1 - K_2$ is due to the presence of sulphate ions in agar solution used by Bolam. The sulphate removes a part of lead nitrate as lead sulphate, and thus lowers its conductivity considerably. The effect of this is to decrease the values given in column 7. On the other hand, it increases the values given in column 6 due to a secondary reaction proceeding simultaneously as indicated below:—

Due to this secondary reaction, a part of the lead nitrate is used up in removing the sulphate leaving a portion of potassium iodide unused, when the latter is mixed with lead nitrate to produce lead iodide. The result of this is that the values in column 5 give us the conductivities of a mixture of lead iodide, potassium nitrate, nitric acid, potassium iodide and lead sulphate and not of lead iodide and potassium nitrate alone as was assumed by Bolam. The presence of unused potassium iodide in place of lead iodide gives us higher values in column 5. Hence the values recorded in column 6 are correspondingly high. With pure agar, we should expect to get much lower values for lead iodide in the ionic state than those recorded here from Bolam's observations.

The second evidence brought forward by Bolam is that the conductivity of a mixture of lead nitrate and potassium iodide remains constant up to a certain concentration and lead iodide in these mixtures exists largely as free ions.

From Bolam's own observations, we have calculated a relation between the concentration of lead iodide in agar and the diminution in conductivity with time. The results obtained are given in Table A. In order to compare these with the diminutions observed in case of lead iodide in conductivity water, Table B has been calculated from the results recorded in Table V of Bolam.

TABLE A.

Conc. of PbI ₂ in agar.	Time.	Diminution.
3'173-10'67		No diminution with time.
10'87	28 hrs.	29
	*28 "	70
11'58	25 "	125
	*24 "	107
12'62	4 "	150
	*25 "	133

TABLE B.

Conc. of PbI ₂ in H ₂ O.	Time.	Diminution.
3'173-3'821		No diminution.
4'008	24 hrs.	1
5'010	39 min.	16
	*24 hrs.	89
	*24 hrs.	77
	*24 hrs.	64'7
	*24 hrs.	88'5

* Separate experiments.

From the above it is clear that even in case of lead iodide in water there is a perceptible decrease in the electric conductivity. If this decrease is negligible and it can be assumed that lead iodide in water remains in the ionic state, there seems to be no justification not to regard lead iodide in agar also to be in the same state, as the diminution in the latter case is proportional to its concentration. Hence, Bolam's assumption that lead iodide in agar (in those solutions that have a constant conductivity) remains in the ionic condition, does not carry conviction in the light of the above observations. The conductivity remains constant up to $C=10'67$. Beyond this the diminution is perceptible. If it is assumed that lead iodide up to $C=10'67$ remains in the ionic state, beyond this concentration it can by no means be assumed to be so. One interesting point that arises from this assumption is the nature of the condition in which lead iodide remains between $C=10'67$ and $C=12'62$, the limit at which lead iodide immediately turns pale yellow.

In our opinion the constant conductivity at lower concentrations of lead iodide is not due to the salt being in the ionic state but is due to the high protective action of agar at these concentrations; on the other hand, at higher concentrations of lead iodide the decrease in conductivity may be due to the gradual adsorption of potassium nitrate by particles of lead iodide formed on standing due to lesser protective action of agar.

Hence from a more critical study of Bolam's own observations, it is difficult to support the conclusions arrived at by him.

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In order to compare the results obtained from the electric conductivity data, we have measured the amount of silver present as ions in the sparingly soluble silver salts by *E.M.F.* determinations. The same preparation of gelatine and of an equal concentration as used in the conductivity experiments, has been employed. The *E.M.F.* has been determined by measuring the *P.D.* of a cell of the type given below.

From the value of the *E.M.F.*, the concentration of silver ions has been calculated. The results obtained are given below.

Experiments with silver bromide.

TABLE VIII.

	Concentration of gelatine = 0.5 per cent.	Temperature = 20°	
No.	Conc. of AgBr : normality × 10 ⁴	Conc. of Ag present as ions : normality × 10 ⁴	Percentage of Ag as ions.
1.	10000	1.10	0.0119
2.	5000	1.156	0.0231
3.	2500	1.185	0.0454
4.	1250	1.125	0.09
5.	625	1.114	0.19

From the above table it is clear that the amount of silver present in the ionic condition is never more than 0.2 per cent. even when the concentration of silver bromide is considerably varied. Moreover the amount of silver present in the ionic condition almost proportionately increases with the decrease in the concentration of silver bromide. Though the quantity of silver as ions is so small in the above cases, it is about 1.4 times the quantity soluble in pure water. From the foregoing experiments, it is absolutely clear that almost cent. per cent. of AgBr exists in a condition other than ionic, and we are strongly of opinion that this large amount of silver is in the colloidal state.

Experiments with silver iodide.

Similar experiments were performed with silver iodide. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE IX.

Concentration of gelatine=0.5 per cent.			Temperature=20°
No.	Conc. of AgI : normality $\times 10^6$.	Conc. of Ag present as ions : normality $\times 10^6$.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
1.	4000	8.38	0.21
2.	3000	7.22	0.24
3.	2000	5.76	0.29
4.	1000	3.67	0.37

In this case, the amount of silver present in the ionic condition is less than 0.5 per cent. Here also, we find that almost all the silver salt is in a condition other than ionic. In the conductivity experiments, we always obtained a *negative* value for the conductivity of silver iodide, which indicated that almost all the salt is in a colloidal state, a conclusion that is completely corroborated by results obtained from *E.M.F.* measurements as given in the above table.

The results obtained with silver cyanide are given below.

Experiments with silver cyanide.

TABLE X.

Concentration of gelatine=0.5 per cent.			Temperature=20°
No.	Conc. of AgCN : normality $\times 10^6$.	Conc. of Ag present as ions : normality $\times 10^6$.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
1.	10000	16.52	0.165
2.	5000	8.15	0.063
3.	2500	4.86	0.194
4.	1250	3.65	0.292
5.	625	3.27	0.523

From the above table, it is clear that the amount of silver in the ionic condition is never more than 1 per cent, whereas from results on electric conductivity experiments, the percentage of silver in the

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ionic condition is with certain concentration of silver bromide as high as 2.5.

The following table gives a comparison of the results obtained with silver cyanide by both the methods.

TABLE XI.

No.	Conc. of AgCN : normality $\times 10^3$.	Percentage of Ag present in the ionic condition.	
		From electric conductivity data.	From <i>E.M.F.</i> measurements.
1.	10000	2.5	0.165
2.	5000	1.95	0.63
3.	2500	1.6	0.194
4.	1250	0.62	0.292

The following results were obtained when silver chloride was the sparingly soluble salt used.

TABLE XII.

Concentration of gelatine = 0.5 per cent. Temperature = 20°.

No.	Conc. of AgCl : normality $\times 10^3$.	Conc. of Ag present as ions : normality $\times 10^3$.	Percentage of Ag as ions.
1.	10000	2.59	2.59
2.	5000	37.2	0.744
3.	2500	3.9	0.156
4.	625	3.15	0.504

The amount of silver present in the ionic condition is never more than 3 per cent.—a conclusion which was arrived at while measuring the electric conductivity of AgCl in gelatine. (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 175).

Summary.

1. Measurements of electric conductivities of silver chloride bromide and iodide of different concentrations in gelatine prove that the observed conductivity is much less than the conductivity calculated on the assumption that the above silver salts exist as ions in the gel. Exactly similar results were obtained with silver chromate and silver chloride in gelatine previously.

2. From the electric conductivity results it has been found out that in the case of silver chloride and iodide the conductivity of a mixture of the silver salt and potassium nitrate is less than the conductivity of potassium nitrate alone, while in the case of silver cyanide the amount of silver present in the ionic condition never exceeded 2.5 per cent.

3. From the results obtained by *E.M.F.* determinations, it has been found out that in the case of silver chloride, bromide, iodide and cyanide the amount of silver present in the ionic condition never exceeded more than 3 per cent. even when the concentration of the sparingly soluble silver salts was considerably varied. We are of opinion that the rest 97 per cent. of Ag exists in a colloidal condition.

4. The hydrogen-ion present in gelatine (pH 5.0) cannot dissolve the sparingly soluble silver salts examined, and hence in the cases of silver bromide, iodide and cyanide the amount of free silver ions present with these salts is much less than in the case of silver chromate in gelatine.

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